

D6.2. Project website, logo, and social media accounts

Work Package **WP6 - Communication, dissemination, and exploitation**

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All Partners

Report Description **This document contains the description of the project website, logo, and social media accounts designed for the SuperBark project (Grant Agreement No. 101112447). The design and content of the website, logo, and social media accounts have been developed by CLIC Innovation with the collaboration of the whole consortium. This document presents a detailed description of the website communication strategy, structure and design, navigability, and content development process for the project website and social media accounts as well as the design process and user guide of the project logo.**

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
Adler	Adler-Werk Lackfabrik Johannberghoffer GmbH & Co KG
BIC	Bio-Based Industries Consortium
CBE JU	Circular Bio-Based Europe Joint Undertaking
CLIC	CLIC Innovation Ltd.
FHG	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Forderung Der Angewandten Forschung EV
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
Goricane	Goricane Tovarna Papirja Medvode d.d.
HFA	Holzforschung Austria Osterreichische Gesellschaft Fur Holzforschung
ICP	Inštitut za Celulozo in Papir
KEAS	Kastamonu Entegre Agac Sanayi ve Ticaret Anonim Sirketi
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIST	Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology
Metsä	Metsäliitto Osuuskunta
RTU	Rigas Tehniska Universitate
Tecnalia	Fundacion Tecnalia Research & Innovation
VTT	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd.
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document contains the description of the SuperBark project website, logo, and social media accounts designed for the SuperBark project. The design and launch of the website, logo and social media accounts are part of the Task 6.1 “Communication and dissemination plan, channels, and materials” within the WP6 “Communication, dissemination, and exploitation”. This document contains a detailed description of the website communication strategy, structure and design, navigability, and content development process for the project website and social media accounts as well as the design process and user guide of the project logo.

Operational as of Month 3, the project website, accessible at <https://superbark.eu>, has a key role in communication and dissemination of the project results and findings as well as in creating the overall impact of the project. The website serves as a central information point for the various stakeholders and media; it has been designed to be the main information repository for the project, its objectives, results and findings, and all activities related to its developments and progress. All communication materials and any other non-confidential documentation related to SuperBark will be either published on or linked to the project website.

Established by Month 3, the SuperBark social media accounts (LinkedIn and X) support the project objective of achieving a wide outreach and engaging target stakeholders. The social media channels are used as a tool to announce project activities, such as achievements, upcoming events and workshops, and to drive traffic to the project website. Both the website and social media accounts will be managed and updated regularly during the project lifetime by CLIC. All partners will support and contribute to the content creation, share their progress and other activities.

The communication channels and materials follow a simple and recognizable visual brand created for the project. The SuperBark logo and visual identity (including colours, typography, graphic elements, and images) are designed to portray a modern geometrical look and feel to reflect the versatile industry applications of the project results, and to attract audiences from industry, academia, public bodies, and the general public. The design of the logo has been developed by CLIC in collaboration with the whole consortium.

1. Introduction

This deliverable contains the description of the project website, logo, and social media accounts that have been designed for the SuperBark project. The design and launching of SuperBark website, logo, and social media channels are part of the Task 6.1 “Communication and dissemination plan, channels, and materials”, within the WP6 “Communication, dissemination, and exploitation”. The project website, logo, and social media accounts have been established and are operational as of Month 3. The project website has been created to serve as a central information point for the various stakeholders and media. It has been designed to be the main information repository for the project, its objectives, results and findings, and all activities related to its developments and progress. All communication materials and any other non-confidential documentation related to the SuperBark project will be either published on or linked to the project website. Project partner CLIC is responsible for managing and updating the website as well as for coordinating the content creation with all partners.

The website communication strategy was designed around key questions that external visitors to the website might have:

- **WHY** - Highlight the background, importance, and purpose of the project: creating widespread visibility for bio-based alternatives and their benefits and opportunities for different end-uses to boost awareness, acceptance, and uptake of these solutions by businesses and customers on both regional, national, and European levels and beyond.
- **WHAT** - Provide a description of the project’s methodology and activities.
- **WHO** - Present the consortium working to achieve these objectives.
- **HOW** - Describe SuperBark results and impact along the project’s development.

All this information appears or will appear on the website. The content and messages incorporated have been defined with the purpose of reaching different audiences, including the general public, scientific community, industry, and policymakers with the objective to benefit from the project results.

2. Target Audience

The website will be provided with information matching the interests and needs of each target group and subgroup. Clear headings and subheadings support intuitive navigation to help visitors to find content that is pertinent to them. Target groups, objectives, and content are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Target groups, objectives, and content.

Target group	Objectives and content
Market / Industrial stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generate interest among early adopters. - Wide outreach and cooperation with value chain actors. - Promote uptake of individual project results. - Get feedback from target audience, provide solutions to perceived risks. - Share success stories, foster sustainability in the forest industry sector.
Citizens and Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness raising campaigns with various activities targeting citizens among other stakeholders (see D6.1). - Educate and deepen understanding of environmental, health, and performance impact of new bio-based adhesives and coatings solutions. - Illustrative and didactic graphic and video materials.

Scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inform about the scientific project results. - Education and training of new experts in bio-based adhesives and coatings. - Sharing results, knowledge diffusion with other experts, opening further research paths. - Getting feedback and new contacts with academic and non-academic experts and working groups.
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suggestions of actions and improvements to overcome local, national and EU-level regulatory barriers preventing uptake of bio-based alternatives, if needed.
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness campaigns aiming for a wide coverage at local, national and EU-level. - Usefulness of EU R&D and initiatives like CBE JU and BIC. - Illustrative and didactic graphic and video materials.
Other CBE JU, BIC, and Horizon Europe projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure synergies and enable wide exploitation to enhance the use of new knowledge in bio-based material solutions beyond the project.

A full description of target groups, key messages, channels and tools of communication, dissemination and exploitation is presented in D6.1 Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities.

3. Measuring Impact

As stated above, the project website has an important and central role in communication and dissemination of the results and findings of SuperBark. The overall impact will be measured through a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that are presented in Table 2 for the whole project duration (48 months). A full set of communication and dissemination KPIs is presented in D6.1 Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities.

Table 2. Website-related KPIs.

Means	Target Audience	KPI
Website	All stakeholders	No. of visitors: 4000
Newsletter	Industry, academia, public bodies, decision makers	No. of publications: 8 No. of subscribers: 200 No. of views: 400
Press releases	All stakeholders	No. of publications: 3-4 No. of contacted media: 500
Promotional materials: presentations, leaflets, brochures etc.	All stakeholders	No. of publications: 7-12 online versions No. of downloads: 100
Social media (LinkedIn, X)	Media, general public, value chain actors, industry, academia, public bodies	No. of followers: 400 (all channels in total) No. of posts: 50 (per channel)
Videos	All stakeholders	No. of videos: 1-2 No. of views: 250
Blog posts	Industry, academia, public and funding bodies, decision makers, media, general public	No. of publications: 8-15 No. of views: 400
Podcast series	Industry, academia, public and funding bodies, decision makers, media, general public	No. of publications: 4-6 No. of listening sessions: 200
Scientific publications	Academia, industry	No. of peer-reviewed papers: 5-10

3.1. Website analytics and GDPR compliance

To generate the needed statistical data and to extract analytics on the performance, SuperBark website is using Google Analytics. Statistical data will be collected and analysed to identify any needed changes and to optimise the user experience on the website. The same data will be used for reporting the progress of the website related KPIs.

In accordance with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the website's Privacy Policy and Cookie Policy are available on the website and will be kept up to date. The website uses cookies to collect and analyse information on site performance and usage, as stated in Figure 1. The website footer has clear and visible links to access this information.

Figure 1. Website Cookie Consent Policy

4. Project website

The SuperBark website is accessible at <https://superbark.eu>. The domain name was reserved at the very beginning of the project, on September 19, 2023, alongside with the creation of the project e-mail address, info@superbark.eu. The .eu domain was chosen to emphasize the European aspect of the project.

The website was published by M3 (November 30th, 2023). The website will be managed and updated regularly during the project lifetime, and it will remain accessible for two years after the project's completion. The website is presented in English as it is the official project language set by the Grant Agreement.

4.1. Website structure and content

The SuperBark project website is characterised by its easy navigability, simplicity, and user-friendly features. Intended to be an informative website, and according to the project's needs to update information, this organisation or internet architecture allows the different audiences to learn more about the project.

In the menu, the following sections have been created: About, Publications, News & Events, and Contact. The entire website structure is presented in Table 3 below. As the project is still in its early stages, some of the pages and sections shown in Table 3 are not currently visible to visitors due to a lack of appropriate content. They will be reactivated once relevant content has been fed onto the website.

Table 3. Website structure.

HOME	ABOUT	PUBLICATIONS	NEWS & EVENTS	CONTACT
	Project	Press releases	News & Blog	
	Partners	Newsletter	Events	
	WP Structure	Documents for download		

The website encompasses a variety of materials that allow a successful communication and dissemination amongst the partners and towards the various target audiences. The 'About' section comprises three (3) subsections to introduce the project: Project, Partners, and WP Structure. The 'Project' page includes two (2) subsections: Objectives and Impact. These briefly present the goals and measurable impact of the project to let the audience understand what the project is about and why it is innovative and marketable. The 'Partners' page includes a description of each organisation involved in the project with contact e-mails, links to their website and social media. A partner map is included in this page to better illustrate the partner location and the territorial and regional aspect of the project. The 'WP Structure' page includes the project Methodology and a description of each WP in the project (WPs 1-6).

An 'Applications' subsection is planned to be added by M12 of the project. The page is foreseen to include descriptions of the relevant project KERs and their applications in various industry sectors, such as furniture, construction, transport, and packaging, in more detail. This page will be further developed in cooperation with the corresponding project partners involved, and with relevant target industry users in mind (e.g., from the forest, chemical or packaging industry).

On the 'Publications' section, there are three (3) subsections: Press releases, Newsletter, and Documents for download. These will be used to organise all the produced materials and documents to be easily found and available for open use by any interested stakeholders. Once promotional materials or public project reports will be produced and available, these will be added to the 'Documents' page to download. Public deliverables and reports will also be uploaded once they are approved.

The 'News & Events' submenu is divided into two (2) subsections: News & Blog and Events. The News & Blog -page will include regularly posted news about the project, which revolve around topics such as: the objectives of the project, the progress of the work carried out, upcoming events and workshops, publications, released newsletters or blog posts, etc. The page will also feature blog posts co-written by the project partners, other collaborators, and stakeholders. The Events -page will be widely used to communicate about the upcoming project events and activities.

The Contact -page presents the general email address of the project info@superbark.eu that is managed by the SuperBark Communications team (CLIC), Project coordinator and Communication and Dissemination Manager's contact details, newsletter subscription form, and a contact form for interested stakeholders to use. The messages sent via the contact form will be received in the project info mail info@superbark.eu.

Social media icons (Twitter/X and LinkedIn) appear in the header. The links to access the website Privacy Policy and Cookie Policy are placed in the footer.

The site is not a static tool. It will be further developed, and modifications can be made at any time per the consortium’s request and verification with the Project coordinator. CLIC will regularly update and maintain it, playing a proactive role in checking with partners for the latest news to ensure the regularity and timeliness of the information flow. All partners will contribute to the content creation, share their progress and other activities as part of Task 6.1.

4.2. Design and layout

The SuperBark website has been designed for a user-friendly experience with a layout that enhances the visibility of the project brand. The modern layout follows the overall look and feel set by the developed project visual identity: logo, colours, typography, graphic elements, and images.

The layout is based on storytelling principles that guides the site visitor through the SuperBark story using images, graphics, and key appealing messages that express the value proposition of the project’s technologies, methodologies, and identity.

The SuperBark website has been designed to respond to different user’s behaviours and environments based on device, screen size and resolution, platform, and orientation. The website is responsive to adapt to a variety of devices and screen sizes, such as computers, laptops, smartphones, and tablets. Basic website accessibility testing has been conducted during the site launch.

Figure 2 shows a screenshot of the homepage to get an idea of the overall look and feel of the website. It is intended as an example while the best way to get an idea of the website in its entirety is to visit it at www.superbark.eu.

Figure 2. Homepage of the SuperBark project.

5. Logo

5.1. Logo design

The SuperBark logo was developed to create a simple and impactful visual summary for the project. The logo was designed to include a geometry, which represented the surface coatings and adhesives results of the project, and the range of versatile industry applications (such as in furniture, packaging, construction, and transportation industries). The colours and typography of the logo were chosen to support a modern look and feel of the project to attract audiences from industry, academia, public bodies, and the general public.

5.2. Visual identity

The project visual identity has been developed to build a uniform and recognisable visual brand for SuperBark. The project identity offers a package of templates that will facilitate the building of reputation progressively throughout the project. It will also support the coordination of content creation between different consortium partners and help to attain a uniform look and feel throughout various channels and tools. This includes the project logo and colour palette, graphic elements, and typography, which are presented in the accompanying brand guidelines (see Annex 1). These are being consistently used for the project website and all other communication materials and templates, such as PowerPoint presentations, Word documents, fact sheets, brochures, and posters. Figure 3 below presents the project logo and the designed signature visual appearance.

Graphic elements as a part of the visual appearance

SuperBark signature visual appearance includes the different versions of the graphic background that can be used together with logo. The background designs are fixed, and the graphic elements must not be altered to maintain a consistent visual appearance.

Figure 3. Project logo and signature visual identity

Any communication or dissemination activities in the project, including the project website, will specify that the project has received funding from the European Union, and is supported by the Circular Bio-Based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU) and Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC). The CBE JU, BIC and EU emblems will be displayed alongside a funding statement and disclaimer on all SuperBark related communication materials and channels, as specified in the CBE JU communication guidelines. These instructions are gathered into the EU Funding Acknowledgement Guidelines prepared for the SuperBark consortium (see Annex 3).

6. Social Media Accounts

A social media presence has been established for SuperBark (by M3) on:

X: https://twitter.com/SuperBark_EU / @SuperBark_EU

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/superbark/> / @SuperBark

Social media are important for the communication and dissemination of the project since the outreach and engagement of stakeholders is of utmost importance in order to attain the overall objectives of SuperBark. In addition, having a broad range of networks ensures a wide dissemination to different target audiences. Content will be posted on social media regularly from the very start of the project to increase outreach. Social media channels are used as a tool to announce project achievements, upcoming events, workshops, etc. Most importantly, they are utilised to drive traffic to the project website with the use of different calls to action included in the posts (e.g., More information on our website, Visit our website to learn more, More information and registration on our website, etc).

The social media accounts will be managed by CLIC with support from the partners. Consortium partners are encouraged to follow the project social media channels and engage with them as much as possible. Whenever possible, the partners will share posts on their own corporate websites and social media networks, to further extend the outreach.

WP6 has prepared and provided (by M3) the consortium with a specific guide for using the different social media channels for project purposes and for maximising the impact of the social network. It includes the links, handles and hashtags for SuperBark social media profiles, recommends other handles or hashtags to use in posts (notably CBE JU, BIC and Horizon Europe related handles), as well as tips or good practices to take into consideration when posting via partners' corporate or personal accounts. The guide is meant as a living document to be updated and completed with relevant information throughout the project, whenever necessary. The social media guide can be found in its entirety in Annex 2.

7. Annexes

The following annexes are added to the final version of this document:

Annex 1 – Brand Guidelines

Annex 2 – Social Media Guidelines

Annex 3 – EU Funding Acknowledgement Guidelines

Annex 1 – Brand Guidelines

Brand guidelines

11/2023

Visual appearance

Logo	1–2
Colours.....	3
Typography	4
Images	5–8
Graphic elements	9
Project logos.....	10

Clear space and permitted use of the logo

Four-colour

Black

Negative

Clear space

Permitted use of the logo, colour versions

R=23 G=23 B=195	R=0 G=187 B=227	R=0 G=128 B=189	R=235 G=224 B=213	R=223 G=61 B=61	R=177 G=58 B=26	R=50 G=25 B=8
#1717C3	#000EDD	#0080BD	#0080BD	#FF3D3D	#B13A1A	#321908
C=95 M=77 Y=0 K=0	C=71 M=0 Y=8 K=0	C=83 M=39 Y=5 K=0	C=9 M=12 Y=17 K=0	C=0 M=85 Y=69 K=0	C=22 M=86 Y=98 K=14	C=55 M=74 Y=76 K=81

Helvetica Neue

Regular
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZÅÄÖ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyzääö
 1234567890

Italic
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZÅÄÖ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyzääö
1234567890

Medium
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZÅÄÖ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyzääö
1234567890

Medium italic
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZÅÄÖ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyzääö
1234567890

Bold
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZÅÄÖ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyzääö
1234567890

Images

Our images are fresh, clean and clear in colour. Strive to find images that have a calm and balanced colour scheme, layout and content.

Softwoods – Pine and Spruce

Feedstock, extraction and production

Surface Coatings and Adhesives

Industry Applications and Products

Graphic elements as a part of the visual appearance

SuperBark signature visual appearance includes the different versions of the graphic background that can be used together with logo. The background designs are fixed, and the graphic elements must not be altered to maintain a consistent visual appearance.

Project logos

All materials must always include the project logos with the layout shown in the example.

The project is supported by the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking and its members.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CBE JU. Neither the European Union nor the CBE JU can be held responsible for them.

Annex 2 – Social Media Guidelines

SuperBark Social Media

Social Media Guideline for the Consortium

11/2023

1. SuperBark Profiles

LinkedIn and Twitter/X

LinkedIn

SuperBark on LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/superbark/>

Handle: @SuperBark

Hashtag: #SuperBark

Twitter/X

SuperBark on Twitter/X: https://twitter.com/SuperBark_EU

Handle: @SuperBark_EU

Hashtag: #SuperBark

2. Recommendations & Tips

Handles and Hashtags

Project Handles:

@SuperBark_eu (Twitter/X)

@SuperBark (LinkedIn)

CBE JU Handles:

@CBE_JU (Twitter/X)

@Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU) (LinkedIn)

BIC Handles:

@biconsortium (Twitter/X)

@Biobased Industries Consortium (BIC) (LinkedIn)

Horizon Europe Handles:

@HorizonEU (Twitter/X)

@Horizon Europe (LinkedIn)

Recommended Hashtags

#SuperBark

#CBEJU

#HorizonEU

#horizoneurope

#BIC

#euproject

#research

#innovation

#coating

#adhesive

#biobased

#health

#safety

#bioeconomy

#circulareconomy

#sustainability

#solutions

#woodmaterials

#treatment

#furniture

#construction

#packaging

#transport

#consumerproducts

#environment

Tips

- Always use the **@SuperBark** handle when posting about the project through partner social media channels. This will send us a notification and we can reshare your posts!
- You can also tag **@CBE_JU** or **@HorizonEU**. CBEJU or Horizon Europe may retweet or share project posts on their channels.
- Use **#SuperBark**, **#CBEJU**, **#HorizonEU** or **#horizoneurope** hashtags to increase visibility
- Like, comment and share (with or without your comment) the posts through partner social media channels.
- *Consider also the option of sharing with a comment in your native language for wider outreach!*

SuperBark Social Media Guide

WP6 Laura Turpeinen

Created: 23.10.20223

List of changes

Date	Description of changes

Annex 3 – EU Funding Acknowledgement Guidelines

Acknowledging EU Funding in SuperBark Activities

Guide for the Consortium

11/2023

Acknowledgement of funding is a contractual obligation

Projects funded under the Horizon Europe programme, via CBE JU call 2022 onwards, must follow these guidelines:

- All beneficiaries, managing authorities and implementing partners of EU funding must use the **EU funding body logos, funding statement and disclaimer** in their communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programmes.
- The EU funding body logos are the most important visual brand used to acknowledge the origin and ensure the visibility of EU funding. **Apart from these logos, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight EU support.**

Acknowledgement of funding is a contractual obligation

- Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, **communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support** and display the funding body logos, funding statement and disclaimer (translated into local languages, where appropriate).
- The funding body logos must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.
- Breach of contract obligations may lead to reduced grant!

Funding Statement

The project is supported by the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking and its members.

Use the above funding statement:

- In all activities: media relations, conferences, seminars,...
- On all information material: website, publications, posters, presentations, roll-ups,...
- In all formats: paper, digital,...
- On all supports: infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major results funded by the grant

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CBE JU. Neither the European Union nor the CBE JU can be held responsible for them.

Use the above disclaimer in all communications activities.

Use of Funding Body Logos and Texts

In SuperBark context, please use the following version of the funding bodies' logos and texts together:

The project is supported by the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking and its members.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CBE JU. Neither the European Union nor the CBE JU can be held responsible for them.

This element of funding body logos and texts is already added onto all SuperBark communications materials and templates.

Links

- Funding body logo & texts to download: [SuperBark Funding body logos and texts.png](#)
- Full CBE JU, EU and BIC Emblems & Statements Communication Guidelines: <https://www.cbe.europa.eu/system/files/2023-02/communication-guidelines-for-CBE-projects-speaker-notes.pdf>
- More on CBE JU Visual Identity: <https://www.cbe.europa.eu/system/files/2023-03/CBE-JU-visual-identity-web.pdf>

More info

Link to brand guidelines: [SUPERBARK Visual Guide.pdf](#)

Acknowledging EU Funding in SuperBark Activities – Guide for the Consortium

WP6 Laura Turpeinen

Created: 23.10.20223

List of changes

Date	Description of changes